

Semi-solid-state Li-ion batteries functionally integrated in composite structures for next generation hybrid electric airliner

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Nomenclature

Acronym / Short Name	
CCF	Coated Carbon Fibres
CF	Carbon Fibre
HEA	Hybrid electric aircraft
RMS	Reinforced Multilayer Stack
SB	Structural Battery

1. Introduction

The scope of the SOLIFLY project is to deliver the first aeronautic stiffened panel with an **integrated semi-solid-state battery**, paving the way for making Structural Batteries (SB) a useful technology for the next generation hybrid electric airliner. In the project two SB/cell concepts have been investigated:

- Concept #1: multi-functional materials with a high degree of integration-Coated Carbon Fibers (CCF).
- Concept #2: multi-functional elements with a medium degree of integration-Reinforced Multilayer Stack (RMS).

In the first concept, coated carbon fibres act as structural and electrically conductive components; the second concept consists of laminated structural electrodes.

This deliverable is the outcome of the work performed in the WP 4.3 “*Scalability towards the HEA and technology roadmap*” lead by CIRA.

It includes assessment of the possible scalability of the structural battery’s concept (developed and demonstrated in WP2 & WP3), with respect to WP1 requirements; analysis of the possible update of the classical building block for the certification of composite structures (EASA AMC 20-29) in presence of structural batteries; definition of the technology roadmap for structural batteries to be applied to the composite structures of future HEA (Hybrid Electric Aircraft), based on SOLIFLY technology.

In WP1 the aerospace companies (Piaggio Aerospace, Pipistrel, FACC, Dassault Aviation) of the Advisory Board (AB), with the contributions of CIRA have investigated and shown their current Hybrid Electric aircraft configurations and their studies and perspectives for future HEA, including propulsive and non-propulsive systems e.g., Auxiliary Power Units (APU). In this deliverable, on the same HEA configurations, the effectiveness of the applicability of the SB concepts, developed in the project, is finally analysed.

The output of this deliverable has been presented at the WP4 final workshop in the presence of the Advisory Board, enabling fast transfer of the SOLIFLY results to industry.

2. Upscaling of the SB to commuter and regional HEA

Based on the latest performance of SOLIFLY structural batteries and on their short and long-term prospects, the application of this technology on current and future aircraft is explored to outline a possible roadmap.

Several studies [1], [2], [3], [4], [5] have recently appeared that discuss structural battery technology and its potential for application to the aviation industry. The methodology typically employed in these studies is based on the identification of the aircraft components in which structural batteries can be integrated, on the estimate of the corresponding mass of the battery insert, on the energy and power demand required for a given use and, finally, on the determination of the performance of the battery in terms of energy and specific power. Table 1 summarizes the key findings highlighting the aircraft platform targeted for structural batteries integration, the affected structural components, and the intended energy applications.

Table 1: Estimate of structural batteries specific energy and power for a given energy use as elaborated in [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]

Platform	Seats	Specific energy Wh/kg	Specific power W/kg	Energy stored kWh	SB integrated in	Energy use	Ref.
Airbus E-Fan 1 (Full-electric)	2	79.2	200.7	25.4	Aircraft structure	Propulsive, non-propulsive	[5]
Full-electric concept	2	51.8	103.3	18.6	Aircraft structure	Propulsive, non-propulsive	[5]
Hybrid-electric Concept	4	125.0	400.0	13.6	Fuselage, lower wing	500 nm with minimum standard battery	[1]
Tecnam P2012 (hybrid concept)	9	75.0	n.a.	41.0	75% fuselage mass, 38% wing mass	200/600 nm with minimum standard battery	[4]
A220-100	125	144.0	290.0	21.0	Cabin floor	Galley	[2]
A320	175	90.0	55.0	1125.0	50% aircraft structure	All subsystems electrical loads	[3]

Estimating the mass of the structures in which the structural batteries are integrated can be a very challenging task not only due to general concerns of the repairability and maintenance of structural batteries, but also because many parts currently from metal would need to be replaced with composite materials and a careful analysis is required to verify the loads they must withstand.

The approach taken here is to estimate the area of external surfaces of the aircraft into which structural batteries could be integrated and to multiply these areas by the areal energy density of current and next generation structural battery technology to obtain the total storable energy which, in turn, provides useful information concerning its exploitation for propulsive and non-propulsive needs. This allows also to plan a possible roadmap of the application of structural batteries for several aircraft classes.

The integration of structural batteries in the external surface panels is considered here, excluding surfaces subject to compression or belonging to moving parts.

To estimate the storable energy at a global level, two quantities are relevant: the **areal energy density** and the **aircraft surface area** intended for integration. The first quantity comes from the integration concept

developed in SOLIFLY, the tests carried out and the prospects of the technology. The second can be obtained from the approximate evaluation of the candidate surfaces for integration.

2.1 SOLIFLY structural battery final performance

The development path of the SOLIFLY project included an important evaluation event, the stage gate at project mid-term [6], at which the two SB concepts developed in the project were compared. The preliminary performance of concept #2 (RMS) at stage-gate is reported in Figure 1 for battery cells matching the thickness of a number of CF plies which they replace.

Cell concept #2 (RMS) – current development status				
Number of CF plies	Total thickness of CF plies	Number of battery layers to be integrated	Total thickness of battery insert	areal energy density of battery insert [mWh/cm ²]
		(within ±10% of total ply thickness)		
1 ply	0.184 mm	1	0.200	0.88
2 or 1 ply with double thickness	0.368 mm	2	0.388	1.76
3 plies	0.552 mm	3	0.567	2.64
4 or 2 plies with double thickness	0.736 mm	4	0.754	3.52
6 or 3 plies with double thickness	1.104 mm	6	1.12	5.28

Figure 1: Preliminary (project mid-term) assessment of SOLIFLY structural integration of concept #2 (RMS) [6]

Subsequently, the performance of the structural battery was improved according to Table 2 where a forecast for the next developments is also outlined.

First of all, the density of the CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Panel) without the insertion of the structural battery has a density of 1.58 g/cm³ (1580 kg/m³). Then, the characteristics of both SOLIFLY state of the art (SOTA) and next generation SOLIFLY structural batteries are presented in terms of Gravimetric Energy Density (GED), Volumetric Energy Density (VED), density (CFRP, SB) and effective gravimetric energy density (Δ GED), that is the energy content per weight increase for the SB integration volume, i.e. the part of monofunctional CFRP structure that is replaced by SB: Δ GED = VED / ($\rho_{SB} - \rho_{CFRP}$).

The performance of SOLIFLY state-of-the-art structural battery can be expressed in terms of current values at end of the project (SOTA) and of the maximum technological capability values (SOTA+). The reported performance values were demonstrated for thin laminated battery cells suitable for integration in solid CFRP structures. The SOTA performance (“usable capacity”) was achieved with the developed structural electrolyte that can be cycled stably but is limited by side reactions. (Priority was given in SOLIFLY to developing a reproducible and scalable SB electrochemistry rather than optimizing it for performance.) The SOTA+ performance (“maximum capacity”) was evaluated experimentally with ionic liquid electrolyte showing the capability of the electrochemistry. While the GED and VED are still moderate compared to monofunctional battery cells, they already exceeding other SOTA structural batteries. This is due to its low density cathode, resulting in the energy stored per added weight exceeding the GED of many monofunctional Li-ion battery cells technologies (not accounting for the packaging weight penalty). Furthermore, already SOLIFLY SOTA and SOTA+ shows the potential of SB for low weight impact, i.e. to store **more than 1 kWh per kg extra weight**.

There are three levels of improved technological generations which in the following paragraphs will be referred to as **NG1**, **NG2** and **NG3**:

- in NG1 level the low density NMC cathode of the structural battery is replaced by a high density one and the graphite anode by a graphite/silicon one to increase the specific capacity;
- the NG2 level represents an improvement on NG1 by reducing the weight of passive cell components, mainly current collectors;
- NG3 is increasing the energy density of NG2 by incorporating lithium metal anode.

Table 2: SOLIFLY SB technology – cell concept #2 (RMS): Electrical performance achieved and future improvement steps [7]

		GED [Wh/kg]	VED [Wh/l]	ρ [g/cm ³]	Δ GED [Wh/ Δ kg]	Comment
CFRP		-	-	1.58	-	Δ GED = VED/($\rho_{SB} - \rho_{CFRP}$); amount of electrical energy stored per kg extra weight, assuming that the SB structural capability is sufficient for the respective application/ integration case.
STRUCTURAL BATTERY	SOLIFLY results	SOTA	50	88	1.75	518 Usable capacity of SOLIFLY SB cells: ΔGED is doubling the GED of sota conventional Li-ion battery packs.
		SOTA+	115	200		
	Further improvements	NG1	220	580	2.6	560 Increasing the cell energy density by densifying the cathode and using Si/Gr anode (original plan in SOLIFLY): High GED, ΔGED doubling the GED of sota conventional Li-ion battery packs.
		NG2	290	630	2.2	1020 Reducing the weight of the passive components: GED comparable with sota monofunctional Li-ion cells, ΔGED around 1 kWh per kg extra weight, doubling the GED of future battery packs with advanced solid-state cells.
		NG3	375	1000	2.67	920 Using Li metal anode: VED is 1 kWh/l, ΔGED is little less than 1 kWh per kg extra weight, doubling the GED of future battery packs with advanced solid-state cells.
	<i>This assessment is based on actual results and measurement data from thin, multilayer SOLIFLY RMS SB cells (0.6 mm) matching the thickness of the CF plies in which these SB cells are integrated. Changing the electrode thickness will impact the resulting properties at cell level.</i>					
Key finding: RMS SB cells have the potential of reaching up to 1 kWh per liter and/or kg of extra weight, doubling the amount energy stored per volume or weight impact of future advanced solid-state battery packs (expected 2030+).						

The areal energy density does not explicitly appear in Table 2 but can be easily obtained by multiplying the volumetric energy density (VED) by the thickness of the structural battery, i.e. SOLIFLY considered a total SB thickness of ~1.2 mm integrated into a ~3 mm solid CFRP laminate. Since further considerations are developed upon the areal energy density, Table 3 reorganizes the data of Table 2 to highlight this value and summarize the other performance indicators specified above, the energy densities (GED, VED) and the effective gravimetric energy density (Δ GED). The latter is used to evaluate the weight savings compared to standard (monofunctional) lithium-ion batteries, as will be discussed later in section 2.3.

Table 3: Energy density metrics of SOLIFLY sota and technology improvement levels

Tech level	Gravimetric energy density Wh/Kg	Volumetric energy density Wh/l	Effective gravimetric energy density Wh/ Δ kg	Areal energy density (with regards to 1.2 mm SB thickness) Wh/m ²
SOTA	50	88	518	105.6
SOTA+	115	200	1200	240
NG1	220	580	560	696
NG2	290	630	1020	756
NG3	375	1000	920	1200

2.2 Area of aircraft surfaces for possible SB integration

Structural batteries are assumed to be integrated in the outer fuselage panels, on the lower wing except moving surfaces, and on the cabin floor. The estimation of the area of these surfaces is done in two ways: by developing a generic aircraft configuration and by using published data of selected aircraft configurations.

Indeed, the best way to proceed would be to start from a CAD representation of the aircraft and consider only the surfaces into which structural batteries potentially could be embedded. The Internet provides a number of sites (for example, [8]) from which unofficial CAD representations can be downloaded. While these representations provide a general overview, they may not accurately reflect the original drawings. Caution is advised as the segmentation into surface patches may not align with the desired subdivision. Of course, the ideal would be to obtain the CAD representations directly from the aircraft manufacturer, but this, in general, is unlikely to happen.

The following paragraph illustrates how carry out the estimate starting from a downloaded CAD representation whose quality is considered to be acceptable. The results obtained are then used to verify the other methods presented later. In all cases discussed below it is important to emphasize that the order of magnitude is the true objective of the area calculation and not the precise value.

2.2.1 Surface area from CAD representation

The CAD representation of the Dash 8 – Q400 found on the Internet [9] is quite rich in detail; this is a favourable condition as it was possible to blank the surfaces where structural batteries would not have been integrated. Figure 2 displays the result of this cancellation (grey surfaces are not considered). The fuselage surface has been divided into its three main segments: cockpit, cabin and cone. Transparent surfaces, openings, movable surfaces and the vertical and horizontal tail surfaces are excluded. Figure 3, where side and bottom views are offered, allows to capture those surfaces hidden from the 3D view. The final results are reported in Table 4.

Figure 2: 3D view of the Dash 8 - Q400 aircraft; grey surfaces are not accounted for structural battery integration

Table 4: Area of the colored surfaces of Figure 2

Aircraft surfaces	Area (m ²)
LOWER WING	27.91
CABIN	143.00
NOSE	16.65
REAR	37.73
TOTAL	225.29

Figure 3: Dash 8 - Q400 aircraft; side and bottom views

2.2.2 Fuselage, wing and floor surface area calculation

Fuselage is approximated with three solid geometries as in Figure 4, where the nose, cabin and rear part are represented respectively by a prolate spheroid¹, a cylinder and a cone for which analytical formulae are known and listed below in eqq (1), (2) and (3).

¹ $L_n > b, c$

$$S_n \approx \pi \left(c^2 + L_n \cdot c \frac{\arccos\left(\frac{c}{L_n}\right)}{\sin \arccos\left(\frac{c}{L_n}\right)} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$S_c \approx L_c \cdot 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{b^2 + c^2}{2}} \quad (2)$$

$$S_r \approx \frac{1}{2} \pi \left(b \sqrt{c^2 + L_r^2} + c \sqrt{b^2 + L_r^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$S_{fus} = S_n + S_c + S_r \quad (4)$$

Figure 4: approximation of fuselage

To determine the surface areas some characteristics lengths, such as L_n , L_c and L_r , must be acquainted. Of course, the overall fuselage length (L_f) is given by the sum of the latter lengths. The interface between each fuselage part is an ellipse with semi-axes b and c which when equal lead to a circular cross-section. In particular, $2b$ represents the fuselage width and $2c$ the fuselage height that in the next sections are referred respectively with w_c and h_f .

Another way of calculating the fuselage area is to use relationships from aircraft databases as many authors have done including Torenbeek by defining in [10]

$$S_{fus} = \pi \cdot d_f \cdot L_f \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2}{\lambda_f}\right)^{2/3} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{2}{\lambda_f^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

or in [11]

$$S_{fus} \approx \pi \cdot \bar{d}_f \cdot (L_f - 1.3 \cdot d_f) \quad (6)$$

where the slenderness is

$$\lambda_f = \frac{L_f}{\bar{d}_f} \quad (7)$$

which depends on the equivalent diameter defined as

$$\bar{d}_f = \frac{h_f + d_f}{2} \quad (8)$$

or

$$\bar{d}_f = \sqrt{h_f \cdot d_f} \quad (9)$$

The interplay between aircraft surface wing area, fuselage length, and passenger capacity is intricate and can exhibit substantial variations based on the particular aircraft's design and intended function. There are some general trends that can be observed, but these trends may not hold true for all aircraft due to variations in design and technology.

As far as the wings, the lower surface is computed as

$$S_{wing} = \frac{0.156}{\left(1 + \frac{n_p - 12}{90}\right)} \cdot L_f^2 \quad (10)$$

Many textbooks assume that the floor area per passenger is 0.6 m² [10] and, thus,

$$S_{floor} \approx 0.6 \cdot n_p \quad (11)$$

From the equations above it is clear that a sort of very preliminary sizing of the noticeable aircraft dimensions is necessary, that is, an estimation of the quantities L_n , L_c , L_r , d_f and h_f must be performed. This task can be accomplished either by calculating them starting from empirical or statistical relationships, or by using the values reported in numerous publications or published on specialized Internet sites. The first approach is described in section 2.2.3 and the second one in section 2.2.4.

2.2.3 Estimate of aircraft primary dimensions from generic aircraft configurations

Textbooks allows to determine the possible aircraft dimensions (fuselage length, width and height) on the basis of passenger number and using reference values for seat pitch, seat width, aisle width and seat abreast. In order to perform a simple exercise, the data of Table 5 have been considered for several aircraft: the 9 pax aircraft could be a general aviation aircraft, the 12 pax one could be a business jet, the 19 pax aircraft a subregional commuter, and 40-100 pax aircraft could be regional turboprop or regional jet.

Table 5: Case studies considered for generic aircraft

Pax	n_abreast	Seat pitch (inch)	Seat width (inch)	Aisle width (inch)
9	2	31	17	12
12	2	31	17	12
19	2	31	17	12
40	4	31	18	15
50	4	31	18	15
78	4	31	18	15
100	4	31	18	15

The fuselage inner width (w_c) is computed as

$$w_c = n_{SA} \cdot (w_s + w_a) + (2 \cdot n_{aisle} + 1) \cdot w_a + 2 \cdot w_{cl} + n_{aisle} \cdot w_{aisle} \quad (12)$$

where n_{SA} is the number of seats abreast, n_{aisle} is the number of aisles, w_s is the width of seat, w_a is the width of seat armrest, w_{aisle} is the width of aisle and w_{cl} is the width of clearance taking into account of clearance of passenger shoulder and head. Figure 5 includes a simple scheme for referencing to the lengths defined above.

EASA and FAR recommends typical ranges for w_s , w_a , w_{aisle} and w_{cl} depending on the aircraft class. Some of the quantities requested for calculating the cabin width are specified in Table 5 for the aircraft under investigation; other quantities are taken constant ($w_a=2in$, $w_{cl}=2in$, $n_{aisle}=1$).

The external fuselage diameter can be calculated by using an empirical formula defined in [12]:

$$d_f = 1.045 \cdot w_c + 0.084 \quad (13)$$

Figure 5: typical quantities to size the fuselage cabin width (a) and length (b)

The cabin length is obtained by multiplying the seat pitch (P) by the number of seat rows that comes from the ratio of passenger number (n_p) and number of seats abreast (n_{SA}); this theoretical value is increased by Torenbeek [10] of a factor of 1.35^2 accounting for galley, lavatory and door access.

$$L_{-c} = 1.35 \cdot \frac{n_p}{n_{SA}} \cdot P \quad (14)$$

The length of the fuselage nose and rear can be sized by using a number of empirical formulae; (15) and (16), for example, can be used for fuselage nose and (17) and (18)³ for fuselage rear part.

$$L_{-n} = 1.5 \cdot d_f \quad (15)$$

$$L_{-n} = 2.5 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\max(20; n_p)}{120} \right) \quad (16)$$

$$L_{-r} = 1.6 \cdot d_f \quad (17)$$

$$L_{-r} = \frac{d_f}{\tan \varphi} \quad (18)$$

The fuselage height has been estimated by means of

$$h_f = \frac{1}{5} \cdot L_f + \left(\frac{2}{5} \right)^2 \cdot L_{-c} \quad (19)$$

It should be underlined that these equations are not intended to be used for preliminary aircraft design but they simply serve to provide an initial evaluation of the external surfaces suitable for the structural integration of the batteries. With their application Table 6 is obtained, in which the calculated data are reported in red characters and the input data in black (the same colour code applies to the subsequent tables).

Table 6: Primary dimensions as computed by empirical and statistical formulae

Aircraft	Pax	Length (m)	L_nose (m)	L_cabin (m)	L_rear (m)	Width cab (m)	Height cab (m)	Wing area (m ²)	Floor area (m ²)
1	9	10.51	2.92	5.31	2.28	1.42	1.25	17.82	5.40
2	12	11.57	2.92	6.38	2.28	1.42	1.29	20.88	7.20
3	19	15.82	2.92	10.63	2.28	1.42	1.46	36.24	11.40
4	40	18.07	3.33	10.63	4.10	2.57	1.91	38.84	24.00
5	50	21.47	3.54	13.82	4.10	2.57	2.08	50.54	30.00
6	78	29.49	4.13	21.26	4.10	2.57	2.50	78.27	46.80
7	100	35.26	4.58	26.57	4.10	2.57	2.80	98.08	60.00

² A factor of 1.1 is proposed in [33].

³ φ is the cone angle that is less than or equal to 20° to guarantee a smooth transition between cabin cross section and final section of the tail cone as to avoid boundary layer separation.

2.2.4 Primary dimensions of selected aircraft

Searching for the quantities L_n , L_c , L_r , d_f and h_f on the Internet can be done after selecting some aircraft. This was done with the aim of being in line with Table 6 and for the aircraft of Table 7 some data was found⁴.

Table 7: Primary dimensions of selected aircraft found on Internet sites

Aircraft	Pax	n_abreast	Length (m)	L_nose (m)	L_cabin (m)	L_rear (m)	Width cab (m)	Height cab (m)	Wing area (m ²)	Floor area (m ²)
P2012	9	2	11.80	2.45	6.90	2.46	1.48	1.36	25.4	5.40
Do228	19	2	16.56	2.25	7.98	6.33	1.35	1.55	32.0	9.56
Cessna sovereign	12	2	19.35	2.73	8.39	8.23	1.67	1.72	50.4	7.20
ATR72-600	74	4	27.17	4.00	19.21	6.31	2.77	2.63	61.0	44.40
Q400	78	4	32.80	5.25	18.80	8.75	2.69	1.95	64.0	46.80
CRJ900	90	4	36.20	4.05	21.16	10.99	2.55	1.88	71.1	54.00
E190	114	4	36.24	4.74	25.76	5.74	3.01	3.31	92.5	68.40

Direct comparison of Table 6 and Table 7 on dimensions of same pax aircraft emphasizes the limitations of empirical and statistical relationships: their origin may not be based on fundamental aerodynamic principles or rigorous engineering analysis. It may instead be the result of a data fit or empirical observations for a specific range of aircraft or a certain generation of aircraft.

2.2.5 Computation of surface area and verification

By using the data of Table 6 and Table 7 and approximating the fuselage as proposed in section 2.2.2, the estimation of Table 8 is obtained. The results from the two strategies (that is, data from empirical/statistical relationships vs data on real aircraft found on the Internet) are placed side by side on purpose to show how large the discrepancies can be.

Table 8: Estimate of the total surface area where the insertion of structural batteries is assumed

a) using Table 6 data						b) using Table 7 data					
Aircraft	Pax	Fuselage surf area (m ²)	Wing area (m ²)	Floor area (m ²)	Total surface area (m ²)	Aircraft	Pax	Fuselage surf area (m ²)	Wing area (m ²)	Floor area (m ²)	Total surface area (m ²)
1	9	39.45	17.82	5.40	62.67	P2012	9	49.25	25.40	5.40	80.05
2	12	44.92	20.88	7.20	73.01	Do228	19	101.53	32.00	9.56	143.09
3	19	68.29	36.24	11.40	115.92	Cessna sovereign	12	160.02	50.40	7.20	217.62
4	40	125.93	38.84	24.00	188.77	ATR72-600	74	290.28	61.00	44.40	395.68
5	50	157.41	50.54	30.00	237.95	Q400	78	303.02	64.00	46.80	413.82
6	78	240.06	78.27	46.80	365.12	CRJ900	90	370.96	71.10	54.00	496.06
7	100	307.27	98.08	60.00	465.35	E190	114	402.22	92.50	68.40	563.12

A further analysis can be performed by applying the Torenbeek formula which lead to the results of Table 9. Overall, a distinctive underestimation is observed although it must be said that Torenbeek's formula is based

⁴ Data in Table 7 written in black can be found on the Internet; data in red are processed by using empirical formulae of previous paragraphs.

on a rather old statistical database which clearly emerges from Figure 6 where the data in Table 6 and Table 7 are superimposed to the behaviors expected by Torenbeek.

Table 9: Estimate of the fuselage surface area after Torenbeek

a) using Table 6 data			b) using Table 7 data		
Aircraft	Pax	fuselage surf after Torenbeek (m ²)	Aircraft	Pax	Fuselage surf after Torenbeek (m ²)
1	9	35.93	P2012	9	46.99
2	12	43.47	Do228	19	62.72
3	19	61.80	Cessna sovereign	12	90.66
4	40	121.22	ATR72-600	74	208.00
5	50	147.44	Q400	78	252.89
6	78	209.40	CRJ900	90	267.82
7	100	254.01	E190	114	306.18

Figure 6: Verification of the Torenbeek relationships on data in Table 6 and Table 7; solid and dashed lines represent the behavior of L_f/d_f and $(L_n+L_r)/d_f$ with respect to L_c/d_f found by Torenbeek; symbols (with solid and dashed contours) refer to the corresponding behaviors obtained with lengths of Table 6 and Table 7

Anyway, fuselages host transparent surfaces and numerous openings that are not intended for the integration of structural batteries; the same goes for the wing for which, in addition to the exclusion of the upper part because of compression, the moveable surfaces must also be removed. To take this into account, two factors, respectively, of 0.7 and 0.5 are used as in eq. (20) which allows the net surface area to be estimated as reported in Table 10.

$$S_{net} = 0.7 \cdot S_{fus} + 0.5 \cdot S_{wing} + S_{floor} \quad (20)$$

Table 10: Estimate of the net surface area where the insertion of structural batteries is assumed

a) using Table 6 data				b) using Table 7 data			
Aircraft	Pax	Total surface area (m ²)	Total net surf area (m ²)	Aircraft	Pax	Total surface (m ²)	Total net surface area (m ²)
1	9	62.67	41.92	P2012	9	80.05	52.58
2	12	73.01	49.09	Do228	19	143.09	96.63
3	19	115.92	77.32	Cessna sovereign	12	217.62	144.41
4	40	188.77	131.57	ATR72-600	74	395.68	278.10
5	50	237.95	165.46	Q400	78	413.82	290.91
6	78	365.12	253.97	CRJ900	90	496.06	349.22
7	100	465.35	324.13	E190	114	563.12	396.20

At this point, a further assessment on the calculation of the net areas can be made by comparing the data obtained from CAD, generic aircraft configuration and real aircraft published information: for DASH 8 Q400, in fact, all details are available.

Table 11: Comparison of the net surface area for the DASH 8 – Q400 aircraft

Area of aircraft parts [m ²]	Methods		
	CAD	generic aircraft configuration	real aircraft published info
LOWER WING	27.91	49.04	32.00
CABIN	143.00	118.35	97.13
NOSE	16.65	18.43	17.95
REAR	37.73	31.27	97.04
Total	225.29	217.09	244.12

In general, while the total values in Table 11 exhibit a reasonable degree of consistency and the order of magnitude is taken, significant discrepancies emerge when the individual fuselage segments are examined; these variations depend on many factors, including the methodology employed for dividing the fuselage length into segments.

2.3 Estimation of electrical energy stored

After having estimated the area of the surfaces intended for the integration of the structural batteries, with the help of Table 3 where the current and future areal energy density are collected, it is possible to compute the potential storable energy for each aircraft as shown in Table 12 and Table 13 according to two strategies now familiar to the readers.

Table 12: Estimate of the storable energy for the surfaces of Table 10a

Aircraft	Pax	Total surface area (m ²)	Total net surf area (m ²)	Technology level	SOTA	SOTA+	NG1	NG2	NG3
				Areal density (Wh/m ²)	105.6	240.0	696.0	756.0	1200.0
				Energy stored (kWh)					
1	9	62.67	41.92	4.43	10.06	29.18	31.69	50.31	
2	12	73.01	49.09	5.18	11.78	34.17	37.11	58.91	
3	19	115.92	77.32	8.16	18.56	53.81	58.45	92.78	
4	40	188.77	131.57	13.89	31.58	91.57	99.47	157.89	
5	50	237.95	165.46	17.47	39.71	115.16	125.09	198.55	
6	78	365.12	253.97	26.82	60.95	176.76	192.00	304.77	
7	100	465.35	324.13	34.23	77.79	225.60	245.04	388.96	

Table 13: Estimate of the storable energy for the surfaces of Table 10b

Aircraft	Pax	Total surface area (m ²)	Total net surface area (m ²)	Technology level	SOTA	SOTA+	NG1	NG2	NG3
				Areal density (Wh/m ²)	105.6	240.0	696.0	756.0	1200.0
				Energy stored (KWh)					
P2012	9	80.05	52.58	5.55	12.62	36.59	39.75	63.09	
Do228	19	143.09	96.63	10.20	23.19	67.26	73.05	115.96	
Cessna sovereign	12	217.62	144.41	15.25	34.66	100.51	109.18	173.29	
ATR72-600	74	395.68	278.10	29.37	66.74	193.56	210.24	333.72	
Q400	78	413.82	290.91	30.72	69.82	202.48	219.93	349.10	
CRJ900	90	496.06	349.22	36.88	83.81	243.06	264.01	419.06	
E190	114	563.12	396.20	41.84	95.09	275.76	299.53	475.44	

2.4 Potential of SB energy storage at aircraft level

At the time of writing this report section, no detailed information is available on the arrangement of SOLIFLY structural batteries in modules or packs. The basic assumption is that the cells are arranged in panels that are used in the external surfaces of aircraft without any limitations other than the exclusion of compression zones, openings, transparent and movable surfaces. The same applies to structural performance and any maintenance, reparability and safety considerations.

The previous paragraphs have highlighted that the extent of aircraft surfaces used for battery integration is only a part of the total wetted area; furthermore, the approximation in the estimate of these surfaces can be significant. In order to provide a better view regardless of the surface estimate, an approach that reverses the starting data is proposed in Table 14.

Table 14: Savings in weight⁵ and required surface area resulting from integration of structural batteries of different technologies

Storable energy [kWh]	1	Standard battery 2023	SB SOTA	SB SOTA+	SB NG1	SB NG2	SB NG3
Spec energy [Wh/kg]		250					
Effective GED [Wh/Δkg]			518	1200	560	1020	920
Weight [kg]		4	1.93	0.83	1.79	0.98	1.09
Delta weight [kg]		-	-2.07	-3.17	-2.21	-3.02	-2.91
Areal density [Wh/m ²]		-	105.6	240.0	696.0	756.0	1200.0
Needed surf [m ²]		-	9.5	4.2	1.4	1.3	0.8

In practice, the starting point is the storable energy, i.e., the energy that can be used to power propulsive and non-propulsive systems. Once this data is known, the necessary surface area comes from the reciprocal of the areal energy density which has been set for each structural battery technology. Table 14 shows the surface area needed per kWh; therefore, for an exemplary energy storage of 10 kWh, the SOTA structural batteries would need 95 m² of available surface area which does correspond to that of aircraft with less than or equal to 19 passengers (with the exception of the business jet class which in turn requires much more energy per mission) according to the estimate reported in the "net surface area" column of Table 12 and Table 13. On the other hand, NG3 structural batteries would need only 8 m² for the same amount of energy storage, thus making SB application very attractive. The amount of 10 kWh for energy storage is just an example; in reality, the energy from batteries must be seen in the global framework of the aircraft preliminary design where any configuration leading to an increase in wetted area (e.g., boxed wing, strut-braced, ...) would be more suitable for this type of technology.

Since Table 14 is based on the effective gravimetric energy density (ΔGED), it is also possible to calculate the weight savings⁶ with respect to a current standard Lithium-Ion battery with a specific energy (at cell level) of 250 Wh/kg. It is worth noting that the weight savings translate into lower energy requirements per mission. Elsewise a compromise could be sought between the weight savings and the increase in overall energy (for example, to be used as range extender) that would result from carrying on board a standard battery whose weight is equivalent to the weight reduction of the structural battery. However, Table 14 is affected by three types of simplification: first, the weight savings of next-generation structural batteries (NG1-NG3) should be calculated assuming next-generation lithium-ion batteries with specific energy of 400-600 Wh/kg, secondly, the battery thermal and electrical management systems and confinement have not yet been taken into consideration and finally, the composite surfaces are supposed to withstand the same loads without adding any layers other than the battery insert. In addition, a more in-depth assessment of the weight savings should also consider two important aspects: the battery cooling system may be less demanding and thus lighter since the heat is transferred more efficiently from the external surfaces through convection; fewer long cables may be needed when locally connecting electrical loads (e.g., cabin lighting, in-flight entertainment systems, power sockets for charging passengers' electronic devices), contributing to further reduce weight.

⁵ With respect to standard Lithium-Ion batteries (module/pack of 1 kWh)

⁶ Readers may refer to the line "Delta weight" of Table 14.

2.4.1 SOTA technology

SOTA technology would require almost 100 m² of aircraft surface area to store 10 kWh. Only half of this surface area would be needed for SOTA+ technology. This suggests the use of structural batteries only for low-power (non-critical) auxiliary systems.

2.4.2 Next generation technology

With structural batteries of next generation technology (NG1, NG2 and NG3), a surface of 100 m² would provide enough energy (from 70 to 125 kWh) to power non-propulsive subsystems. On regional aircraft, where the available surface area can be in the order of 300-400 m², the most energy-dense structural battery could provide up to 0.5 MWh. Although for this class of aircraft the total energy required for a typical mission is much higher than what could be stored in structural batteries, this still represents an interesting amount also for propulsion as in hybrid-electric systems it could be used in combination with conventional batteries which then would be reduced in size and weight. A nice graphical representation of the data in Table 12 and Table 13 is shown in Figure 7 where correlations of energy stored and weight savings with the aircraft passenger number (which also define the aircraft class) are displayed.

Figure 7: Potential of SB energy storage at aircraft level as function of number of passengers (Pax) in terms of net surface and absolute amount of energy stored (left) and energy stored and weight saved per passenger (right) ⁷

2.4.3 Assessment against the initial requirements

SOLIFLY deliverable D1.1 [13] also includes the initial requirements established by the Advisory Committee partners. With reference to Piaggio AeroIndustries' e-STOL and Pipistrel's PVRK-1 aircraft concepts, both representing the next generation of 19-pax commuters, the energy stored in batteries is combined respectively with that provided by a turbogenerator and a fuel cell stack. The energy storage requirement is in the order of 500 kWh for today and 1 MWh for 2032. With these requirements the use of structural batteries for propulsive needs is only feasible with the most advanced technology (NG3).

2.5 Final comments

From an energy point of view, structural batteries represent a very interesting solution for obtaining weight savings by replacing standard on-board lithium-ion batteries. In particular, new generation

⁷ The graphs of this figure were elaborated by H. Kuehnelt and presented at GA SOLIFLY meeting of 20-21 Dec 2023.

technologies are expected to provide excellent performance and the energy they could store will increase when the integration of structural batteries is not limited to external surfaces, as in this study, but is applied to other structural components of the airframe.

Upcoming SOLIFLY results on the integration of cells into a panel and subsequent tests will better characterize the technological potential developed within the project.

SOLIFLY and MATISSE, two closely interconnected EU-funded projects, are both part of a technological path in which the industrialization of structural batteries is expected beyond 2040 as illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8: proposed TRL step-up following the SOLIFLY project [14].

Of course, testing and further experimentation are key points to understand the full potential of structural batteries whose weight savings will constantly be compared to the easy replacement of standard batteries. Typically, commercial aircraft are designed to be in service for more than 20 years, and batteries for high-frequency use may have a short lifespan, so their replacement is expected within a few months. Consequently, structural batteries must have a lifespan of the order of decades without degradation of mechanical performance to avoid their life cycle from determining the overall life cycle of the aircraft.

The contents of this chapter represent only a very preliminary assessment that needs to be integrated with similar evaluations addressing mechanical properties and safety and certification issues.

3. Upscaling SB to the HEA configurations of the AB (WP1)

In this chapter the electric energy that could be stored using SB integrated in the structural CFRP components of the aircrafts presented as reference by the SOLIFLY Advisory Board (AB) and reported in [13] was evaluated.

The amount of the energy stored in the SB was calculated using the areal energy density (Wh/m²). This parameter was identified in the activities of the WP1 as one of values to measure during the SB technology development thinking that large part of the aeronautical structural components is developed mainly in 2D dimension as skin panels but also spar web, rib web, fuselage floor, bulkheads. The values of areal energy density used for the evaluations in the next paragraphs are the following:

Cell concept #2 (RMS) – current development status				
Number of CF plies	Total thickness of CF plies	Number of battery layers to be integrated	Total thickness of battery insert	areal energy density of battery insert [mWh/cm²]
		(within ±10% of total ply thickness)		
1 ply	0.184 mm	1	0.200	0.88
2 or 1 ply with double thickness	0.368 mm	2	0.388	1.76
3 plies	0.552 mm	3	0.567	2.64
4 or 2 plies with double thickness	0.736 mm	4	0.754	3.52
6 or 3 plies with double thickness	1.104 mm	6	1.12	5.28

Figure 9: Preliminary assessment of structural integration of concept #2 (RMS)

The table in Figure 9, the same as shown in Figure 1 for ease of reading, is contained in [6] and reports a preliminary evaluation at coupon level of the areal energy density (see red circled value) obtained at the time of the stage gate phase of the project. The value herein reported is referred to a CFRP flat panel with thickness equal to 1.104 mm.

On the basis of the previous results some further technology developments were performed also in other linked projects and further improved values have been obtained as reported in [14] and summarized in the following Figure 10, the same as shown in Table 2 for ease of reading (see red circled values).

Structural battery			GED [Wh/kg]	VED [Wh/l]	ρ [g/cm ³]	Δ GED [Wh/ Δ kg]
CFRP					1.58	
SOLIFLY Sota (low density NMC cathode, Gr anode)	usable capacity	50	88	1.75	518	
	max. capacity	115	200		1200	
SB Further improvements	dense NMC cathode + Si/Gr anode	220	580	2.6	560	
	+ ultralight current collectors	290	630	2.2	1020	
	+ Li metal anode	375	1000	2.67	920	

Figure 10: current and expected energy storage performance

In order to have all congruent values in terms of areal energy density and with the same unit, the previous values have been transformed in the following ones:

Table 15: Reference values for the areal energy density

Reference	SB performance	areal energy density (Wh/m ²)
Stage gate value at coupon level (Figure 9)	5.28 [mWH/cm ²]	52.8
SOTA cap. (Figure 10)	88 [Wh/l]	105.26
NG3 (Figure 10)	1000 [Wh/l]	1200

At the current level of the SOLIFLY project are not yet available the results of the mechanical tests on the stiffened panels with SB inserted that should confirm or update the values of areal energy density for a more realistic evaluation of the electric energy stored inside typical CFRP aeronautical structural components.

3.1 Piaggio e-STOL HEA Concept

In the AB Piaggio presented a concept of HEA e-STOL 19 seats aircraft. Figure 11 reports the 3-view and its main characteristics [13].

e-STOL Concept

Main characteristics:

- Capacity: 19 pax
- Crew: 1 pilot
- MTOW: 10200 kg
- OEW (w batteries): 7654 kg

Propulsion system

- Turbo generator: 1x1 MW
- Electric motors:
 - Wing tip: 2x250 kW
 - Wing mounted: 2x500 kW
- Battery Energy:
 - Today: 500 kWh
 - Year 2032: 1 MWh

Mission data

- Max speed: 230 KTAS
- Full electric Range:
 - Today: 200 km (100 nm + 45 min)
 - Year 2032: 400 km (100 nm + 45 min)
- Hybrid-electric Range:
 - Year 2032: 1200 km (100 nm + 45 min)

SOLIFLY (GA-101007577)

Figure 11: Piaggio HEA concept - Main Characteristics

For this aircraft has been evaluated the electric energy storage capability by the use of the technology of the SB inserted in the CFRP laminates.

In order to assess the potential of SB for this aircraft, the following criteria were applied taking into account that only the sizing of main components of the wing box is known:

- the fuselage, wing box, vertical tail, horizontal tail have been assumed manufactured in CFRP
- the SB have been considered inserted in the CFRP skin panels of these components but also in some CFRP internal structural components:
 - fuselage floor
 - spar web and rib web respectively for the wing box, vertical tail box and horizontal tail box
- for each laminate the real thickness has been considered and the related areal energy density was estimated by scaling it linearly with respect to the base thickness of the SOLIFLY laminate (see Figure 9)
- the reference thicknesses of the sizing of the wing box have been taken from the high wing, low-tail twin engine turboprop of the Piaggio 19 seats concept developed in CS2 [15] and then appropriately scaled to Piaggio 19 seats e-STOL HEA wing box
- The fuselage of the CS2 Piaggio 19 seats high wing, low-tail twin engine turboprop and the Piaggio e-STOL HEA have essentially the same dimensions and therefore have been assumed equivalent
- Where the thickness of laminate for the other structural components were not known they have been assumed

3.1.1 Wing Box

The architecture of the half wing box is characterized by 3 spars: front (F/S), middle (M/S) and rear (R/S) and 7 full chord ribs and 2 half chord ribs. Regarding the skin panels these have a stringerless configuration being fully collaborative to withstand all the typical loads of a wing box as bending and torsion ones.

The SB have been considered inserted only in the wing box including parts between F/S and R/S not considering leading edge and trailing edge parts.

For each of these structural components has been evaluated the possible energy storage by SB and the results are reported in the following table.

Table 16: P19 HEA - Wing Box - Electric Energy storage by SB

Structural component	Average thickness (mm)	Half Surface (m ²)	SOLIFLY D6.2 (kWh)	SOTA capacity (kWh)	NG3 capacity (kWh)
Lower skin panel	2.78	9.097	2.419	4.838	54.981
Upper skin panel	4.71	9.097	4.098	8.196	93.140
F/S web	3.69	1.65	0.580	1.160	13.187
M/S web	2.90	1.64	0.454	0.909	10.324
R/S web	3.93	1.19	0.447	0.894	10.158
Ribs web	2.45	0.94	0.221	0.442	5.017
Total		24.29	8.220	16.439	186.807

3.1.2 Fuselage

The standard cabin layout is designed to accommodate 19 passengers in the three-abreast configuration, using 31 inches as seat pitch (Figure 12) with 1 forward passenger door and a rear cargo door. The reference aircraft cross section is a 3-abreast rectangular section with an equivalent diameter of 2.32 m.

For the installation of the SB only the part of the fuselage with constant cross section has been considered.

Figure 12: P19 HEA - Standard 19 seats cabin layout

The SB have been considered inserted in the skin fuselage panels and in the floor. For a realistic evaluation, the areas related to the passenger and cargo doors and related to the windows and seat tracks have been removed from the available surface for the inserting of SB. In the following table are reported the results for the energy storage by SB in the fuselage:

Table 17: P19 HEA - Fuselage - Electric Energy storage by SB

Structural component	Average thickness (mm)	Surface (m ²)	SOLIFLY D6.2 (kWh)	SOTA capacity (kWh)	NG3 capacity (kWh)
Floor	3	11.23	1.61	3.22	36.60
Skin panels	2	45.56	4.36	8.72	99.05
Total		56.79	5.97	11.94	135.65

3.1.3 Horizontal & Vertical Tails

The internal structure of the HT and VT is not known. In this case for the evaluation has been assumed that the contribution of the internal structure, spar and rib webs, is in the same ratio with the contribution of the skin panels as on the wing box. Further also for the HT and VT the SB have been considered inserted in the main boxes not including leading edge, trailing edge and movable surfaces. In the following table the results of the evaluation of the energy storage by SB are reported.

Table 18: P19 HEA - VT and HT Energy Electric storage by SB

Structural component	Average thickness (mm)	Surface (m ²)	SOLIFLY D6.2 (kWh)	SOTA capacity (kWh)	NG3 capacity (kWh)
VT lwr and upr skin panels	2	8.75	0.62	1.24	14.13
VT internal structure contribution			0.16	0.32	3.69
Total VT		8.75	0.78	1.57	17.81
HT lwr and upr skin panels	2.5	14.7	1.31	2.61	29.66
HT internal structure contribution			0.34	0.68	7.75
Total HT		14.7	1.65	3.29	37.41

3.1.4 Weight Saving using SB energy storage

The configuration of the Piaggio P19 e-STOL HEA is characterized by the following mission as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: P19 HEA - Design Mission

The propulsive architecture is a hybrid configuration based on a turbo generator coupled with classical batteries with an energy of 500 kWh to be provided during the mission. The batteries at the current status are characterized by a gravimetric energy density of 248 Wh/kg (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: P19 HEA - Battery Pack Solution

The technology of the SB previously applied to the P19 HEA aircraft configuration at the current status as shown in Table 3 and Figure 10 has an effective gravimetric index evaluated as “Wh/Δkg” added to the original structure considering its double function as structure and energy storage. The gravimetric index, as

reported in Table 3 and Figure 10 for the current usable status, is 518 Wh/ Δ kg and with the future improvements can obtain values equal to 920 Wh/ Δ kg.

Using the previous values in terms of gravimetric index related to the SB inserted in CFRP laminate it is possible to evaluate the potential weight saving obtainable using SB inserted in a structural CFRP laminate respect to the classical batteries. On the base of previous evaluations about the energy storage by SB on the P19 HEA configuration it is possible to obtain the following weight saving reported in Table 19.

Table 19: P19 HEA - Weight saving using SB respect to conventional battery cells

SB Solution	Energy Storage by SB (kWh)	Classical Battery Weight* (Kg)	SB Weight (kg)	Weight Saving (kg)
SOTA	33.24	134	64	70
NG3	377.69	755	410	345

* For comparison with conventional batteries the following GED at cell level have been used: SOTA: 248 Wh/kg; future: 500 Wh/kg

3.1.5 Summary and Analysis of Results

In the following table the summary of the electric energy storage by SB evaluated in the previous paragraphs are reported.

Table 20: P19 HEA - Summary of Electric Energy Storage by SB

	EASN CONFERENCE Project Matisse		
	SOLIFLY D6.2	SOTA	NG3
Areal energy density ref. of SB (Wh/m²)	52.80	105.6	1200
A/C Main Component			
Wing Box- (kWh)	8.220	16.439	186.807
Fuselage - (kWh)	5.97	11.94	135.65
Vertical Tail - (kWh)	0.78	1.57	17.81
Horizontal Tail - (kWh)	1.65	3.29	37.41
Total (kWh)	16.618	33.236	377.686

Some useful comparisons are reported in Table 21 in order to give evidence of the contributions of several parts that have led to the previous total results of energy storage by SB. From this table the following outcomes can be obtained:

- The evaluation of the energy storage by SB considering only the contributions coming from skin panels of the fuselage, VT, HT and wing box without taking into account the real CFRP thickness of the structural components can lead to an underestimation of about 60%
- the energy storage contributions by SB of the internal parts of the wing box are about 20% of the whole energy stored in the wing box
- The energy storage contribution obtained from the skin panels of the main components of the aircraft (fuselage, wing box, HT, VT) is about the 80% of the total evaluated.

Table 21: P19 HEA - Evaluation of relative energy storage contributions

Structural component	Energy Ratio (%)	Note
(Wing Box + Fuselage + VT +HT skin panels) / (Wing Box + Fuselage + VT + HT)	80.00	Value of the energy contribution of skin panels only on the total
Internal parts of wing box / Whole wing box	20.71	Value of the energy contribution of only structural internal parts of the wing box on the total wing box
(Wing Box + Fuselage + VT +HT skin panels evaluated all with tck base) / (Wing Box + Fuselage + VT +HT skin panels evaluated with real tck)	40.98	Evaluation of energy contribution without taking into account real thickness of skin panels

3.2 Pipistrel VELIS Electro

The VELIS Electro is world’s first electric powered airplane to receive a Type Certificate (EASA.A.573 TCDS). The two-seater, intended primarily for pilot training, is a game-changing aircraft in terms of technological innovations and cost-efficiency. In Figure 15 is shown the 3-view with the main geometric characteristics. VELIS Electro is a full-electric aircraft equipped with a Pipistrel type certified electric engine E-811-268MVL (TC No. EASA.E.234), developed with partners EMRAX and EMSISO, and Pipistrel’s three-bladed composite fixed pitch propeller P-812-164-F3A.

The 57.6 kW liquid cooled electric engine provides power to the aircraft.

The power is delivered by 400 VDC electric system built around a liquid-cooled in-house developed high performance battery system, which includes two Pipistrel PB345V124E-L batteries connected in parallel, installed in a redundant 2-unit arrangement, total nominal capacity 24 kWh.

VELIS Electro 3-view drawing

Figure 15: 3-view VELIS Electro

Figure 16: VELIS Electro - Battery Pack Installation

One battery pack is located in the nose of the airplane and the second behind the cabin (Figure 16). This ensures redundancy of the power source: in case of battery failure, the malfunctioning battery would get automatically disconnected from the system. A single battery is capable of standalone operation and has enough power capability to support climbing and continuation of flight.

In Figure 17 [13] are summarized the main performances and characteristics of the propulsive system.

Figure 17: VELIS Electro - Main Performance and Propulsive System Characteristics

3.2.1 Summary of Results of Energy Storage by SB

Taking into account the geometrical characteristics previously shown, the capability of energy storage by SB inserted in the structure has been evaluated on the base of the following criteria:

- the fuselage, wing box, vertical tail, horizontal tail have been assumed manufactured in CFRP
- the SB have been considered inserted in the CFRP skin panels of the previous components but also in some CFRP internal structural components:
 - fuselage floor
 - spar web and rib web respectively for the wing box, vertical tail box and horizontal tail box
- As the thicknesses of the several structural components are not known they have been assumed
- For the structural box of the wing, HT, VT, have been done the following assumptions:
 - The quote of energy contribution by SB of the internal parts respect to that evaluated from the skin panels has been assumed equal to that evaluated on the P19 HEA.
- for each laminate the real thickness has been considered and the related areal energy density has been obtained increasing the value linearly proportional respect to the value corresponding to the laminate base thickness (see Figure 10)
- For the fuselage only the part behind the cabin was considered for the evaluation of the energy contribution by SB
- The useful surface ratio between wing box surface (upr + lwr skin panels) and the total wing surface (2 x Wing Sref) has been assumed equal to that of the P19 HEA
- For the evaluation of the fuselage energy contribution at the contribution coming from the skin panels has been added the contribution of 1 m² of floor of the cabin.

In the following Table 22 the summary of the energy storage by SB evaluated for each main structural component is reported.

Table 22: PVS VELIS Electro - Summary of Energy Storage by SB

	EASN CONFERENCE Project Matisse		
	SOLIFLY D6.2	SOTA	NG3
Areal energy density ref. of SB (Wh/m ²)	52.80	105.6	1200
A/C Main Component			
Wing Box- (kWh)	1.49	2.98	33.88
Fuselage - (kWh)	0.39	0.79	8.97
Vertical Tail - (kWh)	0.12	0.23	2.63
Horizontal Tail - (kWh)	0.14	0.27	3.11
Total (kWh)	2.14	4.28	48.59

In the case of SB with capacity based on future improvements (NG3) the energy storage obtained is higher than necessary for the current aircraft that is 24 kWh.

3.2.2 Weight Saving using Energy Storage by SB

Considering the same approach used in § 3.1.4, it has been evaluated the possible weight savings by the use of SB inserted in the main CFRP structural components of the VELIS Electro. In the Table 23 are reported the results. For the capability energy storage by SB in the case of NG3 has been considered the current energy used on the aircraft because in the Table 22 has been shown that SB can cover more than value currently used on the VELIS Electro.

Table 23: PVS VELIS Electro - Weight Savings using SB

SB Solution	Energy Storage by SB (kWh)	(Figure 17) Conventional Battery** Weight (Kg)	SB Weight (kg)	Weight Saving (kg)
SOTA	4.28	21	8	13
NG3	24*	48	26	22

* Considered the current energy used on the aircraft (Figure 17); ** For the comparison the following GED of conventional battery have been used: SOTA GED=205 Wh/kg; Future GED = 500 Wh/kg

3.3 Morphing winglet

During the interactions with the stakeholders participants in Advisory Board of the SOLIFLY project were also indicated as potential preliminary application of the energy storage by SB the possibility to provide power to actuation systems or other service systems of the aircraft not directly linked with the propulsion. In particular considering the ever-increasing increase of electric actuation systems on board aircraft herein this chapter an example of the application of the SB technology application has been shown on an innovative morphing winglet.

In the framework of the Regional Aircraft Research Programme led by LEONARDO and co-funded by the European Union in the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking Programme, the main aim is to validate the integration of innovative and affordable technologies in future regional aircraft platforms.

The Project AIRGREEN2 led by CIRA is a project inside of this CS2 Regional Aircraft Research Programme. The main aims of the project are to develop and demonstrate innovative concepts and methodologies enabling the realization of a wing of new generation. In particular several technologies and their integration at aircraft level have been focused to increase the level of adaptability of the wing, enabling load control and alleviation strategies, and enhancing the aerodynamic performance at the different flight regimes.

CIRA, AIRGREEN2 project led, is involved in the development of a new concept of Morphing Winglet that meets the requirements provided by LEONARDO [16]. Implementing a unique design, the Winglet features 2 independently movable morphing surfaces, capable of increasing the aerodynamic efficiency of the wing by actively controlling the loads at the wing interface (Figure 18).

Figure 18: AIRGREEN2 - Sketch of the Morphing Winglet

The winglet will be tested in flight by LEONARDO after successfully passed all qualification full scale ground tests (Figure 19).

Figure 19: AIRGREEN2 - Morphing Winglet Ground Qualification Tests

Table 24 reports the main structural and actuation power characteristics of the morphing winglet. Considering the inserting of SB in the CFRP fixed skin panels of the winglet, the capability of energy storage by SB in the winglet is shown in the following Table 25 based on the following assumption: the areal density energy is referred to those reported in Table 15 increased by the ratio between the real thickness of CFRP laminate (3.6 mm) and the base thickness (1.104 mm, Figure 10).

Table 24: AIRGREEN2 - Morphing winglet structural and power characteristics

Morphing Winglet	
Total Power for Actuation (W)	400
Total Power for Electronic Devices (W)	200
CFRP Skin Thickness (mm)	3.6
Wetted CFRP Fixed Surface (m²)	1.1

Table 25: AIRGREEN2 - Morphing winglet - Energy Storage by SB

Morphing Winglet Energy Storage by SB			
Surface (m²)	Skin thickness (mm)	Energy Storage (Wh) (based on SOTA usable capacity)	Energy Storage (Wh) (based on NG3)
1.1	3.6	379	4304

Assuming an activation time of the movable surfaces is about 5 sec. for each activation of both surfaces are necessary about 0.83 Wh. This means with the energy storage reported in Table 25 based on current usable capacity of SB would be possible about 456 activations. The result obtained seems to demonstrate that already with the SOTA usable capacity level of the technology of SB this would be adequate to satisfy the energy need of the morphing winglet.

4. Technology roadmap for SB

The maturity of the applicability of SB in the coming years is linked to many factors that need to be taken into account. Following the classical block approach, which is necessary for the certification of composite structures and thus for the composite structures with embedded SB, the following is a summary of what would need to be implemented to achieve the significant **medium-term goals of 2035** and **long-term goals of 2050**, as envisaged by the Clean Aviation, in particular the Clean Aviation Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda [17], which addresses the need for deep decarbonisation and emissions using advanced technologies and fuels.

4.1 Consideration on the building block approach

The results of the work carried out in WP1, WP2 and WP3, have shown that the scalability of structural battery technology at the aircraft level, to assess its potential for propulsive and non-propulsive applications, should require a multidisciplinary approach encompassing materials science, engineering, aerodynamics and more. Furthermore, scalability would depend mainly on the specific aircraft segment considered and the mission profile.

Here, the main steps arising from considerations done in SOLIFLY project, for **improving the scalability of structural aircraft batteries at aircraft level**:

- Strengthen materials research by increasingly focusing on lightweight, high-capacity materials that can serve as both structural components and batteries.
- Improve the energy density and storage capacity of the structural battery to ensure that it can provide sufficient energy especially for the propulsion needs of the aircraft, while minimising added weight.
- Work with aircraft designers and engineers from the early design stages to seamlessly integrate the structural battery into the aircraft design and subsequent maintenance phases (modularity, accessibility, etc.). This integration must maximise space utilisation and ensure that the structural battery elements improve aircraft performance.
- Work with aerodynamics experts to ensure that the integration of structural batteries does not adversely affect the aerodynamic performance of the aircraft; for example, whether or not the integration of such batteries would dictate the curvature requirements of the wing panels compromising aerodynamic efficiency.
- Give top priority to safety and reliability in the design and production processes of the structural battery. Therefore, implement safety and redundancy systems to ensure that the battery remains safe and functional even under harsh conditions.
- Develop scalable manufacturing processes for the production of structural battery components through efficient automation techniques to meet aircraft production requirements.
- Interact with regulatory authorities to establish appropriate protocols to ensure that the structural battery meets appropriate aviation safety and compliance standards.

- Perform extensive testing, simulation and validation, to ensure the performance, safety and reliability of the structural battery, considering the real flight scenarios.

By a **cost-effective point of view**, it is fundamental to invest on

- cost-effective production processes
- and
- material selection

to make structural battery technology financially viable for the aviation industry.

From the **point of view of production**, the new method for battery production developed in the SOLIFLY project is still questionable in terms of scalability, although carbon fibres are already commercially available, electrophoretic deposition and emulsion polymerisation are already established processes on an industrial level, but continued evaluation is required in the further development of processes with regard to scalability, as well as with regard to the more efficient integration of these batteries into the structure.

Certainly, the processes for concept #2 are already used on an industrial level, while for concept #1 the adaptation of cell production processes through the chosen materials, design and structural integration, still needs to be studied in more detail.

The control of temperature and pressure during the curing cycles, compatible with both the requirements of aircraft manufacturing processes, especially in terms of final high mechanical performances, and the battery cell production domain, is the main issue for scalability of the SB especially for more complex shapes (double curvature aircraft panels, etc.).

The **scalability of the SB** under consideration in **complex full-scale aircraft components** is affected by the expected limited performance of the structural batteries under compression loads, which restricts their adoption in components subject to significant values of such loads, as well as by the need to replace them at the end of their lifetime that should imply their application only in the most accessible parts of the aircrafts.

Consequently, is suggested to avoid upper panels in the wings, in contrast to the lower panels of the wings that are usually not compressed in flight. Instead, the use of SB in the fuselage could not imply particular issues on the stress limits, due to the limited aerodynamic loading with respect to the wing.

Difficulty to apply the SB in control surfaces in consideration of their potential concerns in linking these parts to the onboard electrical plant, especially often due to their small size (e.g., for small aircrafts) could hinder their accessibility.

From a **structural point of view**, the introduction of a core with specific characteristics (Nomex honeycomb, etc.) in composite panels with embedded SB is proving, in similar projects (MATISSE), to be more suitable to increase the overall flexural rigidity of the panels and thus improve their ultimate buckling characteristics.

The **necessity to reduce noise and pollutant emissions** around departure and destination airfields and also while flying close to the ground, forces the design of future aircrafts with the capacity to take-off and climb in fully electric modes (i.e., without burning hydrocarbon fuels). This would imply that the total amount of

electric energy should be sized in order to cover take-off and climb, at least to a transition altitude where the noise and chemical emissions produced by the internal combustion engines are less critical.

From a **certification point of view**, for the structural batteries, embedded in composite aeronautic components, there are still no well-defined certification requirements.

According to the EASA AMC 20-29, the strength of the **composite structure** should be reliably established, incrementally through a programme of analysis and a series of tests conducted using samples of varying levels of complexity: this is referred to in industry as the “building block” approach, with testing activity moving from simple samples to more complex elements and details over time. Initial testing helps to avoid early failures in more complex full-scale tests, which are more expensive to conduct and often occur later in the schedule of a certification programme.

Figure 20 shows a typical schematic of building block approach for a composite component, e.g., a fixed wing.

Figure 20: Schematic diagram of building block tests for a fixed wing (EASA AMC 20-29).

Currently there is gap between what is expected from the current building block approach and what is needed which should include the integration of SB into structural composite components. This gap could be overcome by considering the structural part with incorporated SB as a whole component in which the SB material combines both structural and energy storage functions, without in any way absolutely reducing the existing safety level of the same components without embedded SB.

From a manufacturing point of view the SB are under the category of advanced manufacturing, such as all the composite structures, and from a structural point the cells are integrated as a laminate in which a delamination has occurred; therefore, the SB are subject to the current regulations for requiring certification of composite structures.

To date, the Building Block approach of the AMC mentioned above could be supplemented with tests covered in other regulatory paragraphs, other than AMC 20-29, which can be considered suitable to the SB, by evolving them. In particular, referring to the regulations applicable to aircraft equipped with rechargeable lithium-ion, or other lithium-based batteries, and battery systems, in terms of: installation, operation, maintenance, safety assessment, storage and handling, interaction between systems and structure, etc. In

addition, the SB, as energy-storing device, must meet airworthiness requirements applied on aircraft batteries.

In particular, these regulations cover peak temperature phenomena due to systems that generate thermal energy, different thermal expansions, and energy storage functions (ASTM regulations, EASA Special Conditions, Means of Compliance, etc.). The limitation is that these paragraphs do not include a detailed definition of the battery cell 'module' concept, which is crucial for mitigating the effect of thermal runaway (the number of cells in a SB module, the insulation and/or distance between cells, etc.). It is therefore expected that airworthiness certification standards will be updated in this direction, with the support of industrial aircraft manufacturers.

The building block diagram for an aircraft large-scale component, in presence of embedded battery cells, need to be completed with other dedicated tests at different level of complexity, starting from the basic level of coupons. For integrated SB panels, electrochemical tests should be added to the mechanical ones already planned in AMC 20-29 for current composite structures without SB.

In the following, a general overview of the expected tests (Figure 21):

- Electrical battery characterisation (coupon level): characterisation of cell performance and also ageing under ambient conditions
- Functionality of the SB monitoring systems, if applicable (coupon level)
- Electrical battery abuse and safety tests (coupon level)
- Mechanical Characterisations of the SB cells (coupon level): characterisation of structural electrode/cell
- Mechanical tests (coupon level, elements and details): quasi-static loadings (compression, tension, bending, etc.), fatigue tests, low velocity/low energy impact tests, compression after impact tests, etc.
- Tests for the characterisation of thermal properties (elements and details)
- Repairability testing of the SB (elements & details, subcomponent level) to determine the ability and ease of the SB to be repaired during its lifecycle
- Validation tests of dimensioning of subcomponents with the SB (subcomponent level)
- Electrical performance test (component level) for the characterisation of the battery cells before, during and after loading
- Mechanical tests (component level)
- Etc.

Electrochemical performance of the battery cells will be always measured before, during the loading and after the tests. In particular, the above mechanical tests will be interrupted at different load levels to perform

electrochemical tests to assess the evolution of electrochemical performance under load and with the fatigue lifetime of the structures.

Figure 21: Updated Schematic diagram of building block tests for a fixed wing with SB.

4.2 Production process and verification & validation

Towards 2035.

First of all, the production of SB incorporated/integrated into composite panels implies the need to redefine the production processes compared to those applied for the same material system (fibre + matrix) without SB. As expected, this means that the inheritance and consolidation of the production process that the company has learnt over many years for the subsequent use of the components on the aircraft, must be completely revised following again the necessary and in any case lengthy process of manufacturing tests at different levels of complexity, as is already the case for the composite structures, in order to reach that level of reliability and repeatability at least equal to the previous one without SB.

Moreover, the use of both autoclave and out-of-autoclave processing, automated fiber placement processes, etc., are now well established in the aeronautical field to ensure high quality and high mechanical performance as required by aeronautical applications, guarantying the development of repeatable and reliable structures. Therefore, the introduction of SB in aviation presents new challenges and it is crucial that

SB and structural materials and processes are compatible with each other so as not to reduce the structural quality and performance of the parts.

In concomitance with the manufacturing process and its standardization with SB, it is evident that all the **mechanical characterisation** of the original material system (without SB) **at coupon level** (lowest level of the Building Block Approach) also needs to be repeated respect to those ones available for the same material system without SB. Usually, the test campaign for the complete material characterisation at the coupon level takes three to five years.

Together with these mechanical tests a full characterisation of the SB including performance, safety and ageing is needed.

Moving from coupons to components of increasing complexity, **elements and details** of the Building Block Approach (small stiffened panels, parts of wing spars, parts with cutouts, parts of ribs, etc.), in addition to all the mechanical tests already foreseen at this level under the expected loads, the integration of more cells (module) up to the level of pack should be electrochemically tested and characterised taking into account thermal runaway, effect of possible linkage of electrolyte, etc., esp. for safety.

The maturity of the SB at this level of complexity should also be complemented by tests dedicated to its repairability, or in the event that it cannot be repaired, ensuring the modularity and accessibility of the SB components so that they can be replaced. Repairability would also imply the identification of a damage threat assessment of the SB and a damage scenario to be considered in order to verify its performance before and after damage and also after repairability if applicable.

Having reached this level of verification and validation, **from coupon level up to element/detail level**, taking into account an estimated development time of the different previous phases and assuming that aircraft-level integration problems have been resolved in time, **the use of SB** (independently for propulsive and non-propulsive applications) by a structural, functional and integration point of view, **in internal structure components could be considered potentially applicable to the regional aircraft by 2035**. Internal structures mean: spar web, rib web, fuselage floor, bulkheads, etc.

Towards 2050

By increasing the complexity of using the SB at **subcomponent level**, down to the wing and fuselage wetted/outer panels, dedicated tests need to be implemented regarding mainly the verification of the possible vulnerability of the SB to impact damage, the safety risks arising from operating temperatures and different aircraft parts, etc. It is well known that the high sensitivity of the composite structures towards low energy impact damage which are induced by tool drops, runway or ground debris, hailstones, significantly reduces their residual strength under loading conditions, as well as safeguarding against fire threats in certain parts of the aircraft and ensuring critical primary thermal insulation and/or heating where necessary, are a priority. As is already done for the composite structures without SB, an even greater criticality is expected for such structures with SB, as the operation of the batteries could be compromised.

Tests at subcomponent level, under loadings representative of real flight envelopes are expected to verify and validate in presence of impact damages what is requested by the AMC 20-29 in terms of mechanical performances and safety. In addition, electrochemical tests to validate the SB integration at panel level.

In the external panels of the aircraft, the presence of the lightning protection system should preserve the integrity of the SB, but any degradation of the lightning protection system would affect the structural integrity of the SB, as is the case for all electrical systems. In the latter case, the integration of also lightning protection systems on the SB would imply new considerations in terms of manufacturing and mechanical performance, different from those made for structural parts with SB but internal to the aircraft.

Final tests at **component level** will give the right maturity level of the SB for their application to regional aircraft.

Having reached this level of verification and validation, **from subcomponent level up to component level** taking into account an estimated development time of the different previous phases and assuming that aircraft-level integration problems have been resolved in time, **the use of SB** (independently for propulsive and non-propulsive applications) by a structural, functional and integration point of view, **could be considered potentially applicable to the regional aircraft by 2050 also in outer structural surfaces**: outer skin of the wing, fuselage, etc.

4.3 Application to future aircraft and contribution to decarbonization

The European Commission, who launched in 2019 the European Green Deal [18] , aims to substantially reduce greenhouse gas emissions from all modes of transport including the aviation sector with two joint public-private research initiatives (Clean Aviation and Clean Hydrogen). In particular, the SRIA of Clean Aviation [17] clearly states its mission:

“The Clean Aviation JU will develop disruptive new aircraft technologies to support the European Green Deal, and climate neutrality by 2050. These technologies will deliver net greenhouse gas (GHG) reductions of no less than 30%, compared to 2020 state-of-the-art.

The technological and industrial readiness will allow the deployment of new aircraft with this performance no later than 2035, enabling 75% of the world’s civil aviation fleet to be replaced by 2050.”

The same document shows that the regional aircraft are responsible for 5% of emissions and that a reduction of fuel burn must come from new technology implementations, see Table 26. Advanced aircraft need to be developed for EIS (Entry Into Service) by 2035 to enable a complete fleet replacement until 2050.

Table 26: Clean Aviation aircraft category targets [17]

Aircraft Class	Key technologies and architectures to be validated at aircraft level in roadmaps	Earliest EIS Feasibility	Fuel burn reduction (technology based) [8]	Emissions reduction (net – i.e. including fuel effect) [9]	Current share of air transport system emissions
Regional Aircraft	Hybrid-electric, distributed propulsion coupled with highly efficient aircraft configuration	~2035	-50%	-90%	~5%
Short-Medium Range Commercial Aircraft	Advanced ultra-efficient aircraft configuration and ultra-efficient gas turbine engines, ultrahigh bypass (possibly open rotor)	~2035	-30%	-86%	~50%

Previous chapters have presented predictions on weight savings and storable energy enabled by structural batteries up to the **regional aircraft class**. Now, for the same class, the reduction of CO₂ is being studied to demonstrate the type of contribution offered by this technology to the decarbonisation of aviation. For this

[8] Improvement targets are defined as fuel burn reduction compared to 2020 state-of-the-art aircraft available for order/delivery

[9] Assumes full use of SAF at a state-of-the-art level of net 80% carbon footprint, (or where applicable zero-carbon electric energy)

study a concept of regional aircraft considered in the framework of the European Research Program Clean Sky 2 (IADP Regional Platform – H2020 project [19]) is used as reference aircraft and its main characteristics are listed in Table 27.

Table 27: Relevant data of the CleanSky 2 regional aircraft concept

Passengers number	90
Weight per passenger (kg)	99.2 ¹⁰
Design range (nm)	600
Maximum Take-off Weight (kg)	39000
Maximum Landing Weight (kg)	36000
Operating Empty Weight (kg)	25000
Maximum Fuel Weight (kg)	5000

Two cases are investigated, the first of which deals with the use of SB for supplying energy to non-propulsive loads with the propulsion system being based on a conventional gas turbine; in the second case the reference aircraft shall be equipped with a hybrid propulsion system and the SB may contribute also to propulsive needs.

To model a hybrid propulsion system numerically, it is necessary to introduce the hybridization factor φ defined in eq. 21 where P_1 and P_2 are the power of the internal combustion engine and of the battery respectively. All-electric mode corresponds to $\varphi = 1$ ($\rightarrow P_1=0$), conventional internal combustion mode to $\varphi = 0$ ($\rightarrow P_2=0$), and any power mixing is possible by setting $0 < \varphi < 1$.

$$\varphi = \frac{P_2}{P_2 + P_1} \quad (21)$$

A range equation is necessary to correlate the energy spent and the distance covered. In this respect a modified Breguet equation [20] can be used in the form of eq. 22 where L/D is the lift-to-drag ratio, W_{OE} and W_{PL} are the aircraft operating empty weight and the payload weight, e_f and e_{bat} are the fuel and battery specific energy, g is the gravitation constant, $E_{0,tot}$ is the energy spent over the entire mission and η_1, η_2, η_3 take into account the efficiencies of the propulsive components (gas turbine, generator, electric motor, gear box and propeller).¹¹

$$R = \eta_3 \frac{e_f}{g} \frac{L}{D} \left(\eta_1 + \eta_2 \frac{\varphi}{1 - \varphi} \right) \times \ln \frac{W_{OE} + W_{PL} + (g/e_{bat})E_{0,tot} \left(\varphi + (e_{bat}/e_f)(1 - \varphi) \right)}{W_{OE} + W_{PL} + (g/e_{bat})\varphi E_{0,tot}} \quad (22)$$

Eq. 22 cannot be used when $\varphi = 1$ and, thus, for all-electric mode is replaced by eq. 23.

$$R = \eta_1 \eta_3 \frac{e_f}{g} \frac{L}{D} \times \ln \frac{E_{0,tot}}{W_{OE} + W_{PL} + (g/e_{bat})E_{0,tot}} \quad (23)$$

¹⁰ The weight is from [35] where the average passenger weight is 76.2 kg carrying a cabin bag of 7.6 kg and registering a checked luggage of 16 kg.

¹¹ η_1 is the gas turbine efficiency for PPS (Parallel Propulsive Architecture) and the product of gas turbine and generator efficiencies for SPA (Series Propulsive Architecture); η_2 is the efficiency of the electric motor; η_3 is the propeller efficiency for PPS and the product of the electric motor and propeller efficiencies for SPA.

Eq. 22 and 23 are straightforward but they are obtained by introducing a number of simplifications: only cruise segment in steady level flight is considered, $\varphi = \text{const.}$, fuel is entirely consumed.

When **structural batteries are used for non-propulsive needs**, the weight savings are subtracted from the aircraft's operational empty weight, so a further assumption is made: non-propulsive needs are ensured by a conventional battery. In this case, its weight (which is part of W_{OE}) can be reduced according to the energy taken from the structural batteries. Basically, $W_{OE}^* = W_{OE} - W_{savings}$, so that eq. 23 is replaced by

$$R = \eta_1 \eta_3 \frac{e_f}{g} \frac{L}{D} \times \ln \frac{E_{0,tot}}{W_{OE}^* + W_{PL} + (g/e_{bat})E_{0,tot}}. \quad (24)$$

By applying eq. 24 and drawing energy from structural batteries progressively from 0 to 500kWh, Figure 22 is obtained on the basis of today technology and of conventional propulsion system (ICE, Internal Combustion Engine)¹². It is worth recalling the assumptions made about today's technology: a gas turbine efficiency of 0.37, a specific energy of 250 Wh/kg for conventional batteries and an effective GED of 518 Wh/ Δ kg for structural batteries.

In 2035 the following enhancements are supposed: the specific energy of standard battery (e_{bat}) doubles, the effective GED of structural battery is 560 Wh/ Δ kg as per NG1 technology of Table 3, aircraft aerodynamics improves resulting in $L/D=15$, and efficiency of the powertrain becomes $\eta_1 \cdot \eta_3 = 0.39 \cdot 0.816$. Figure 23 shows that the CO₂ reduction is lower than that of Figure 22 because of a reduced gain of specific energy of SB compared to that of standard batteries.

Figure 22: ICE 2023 configuration - fuel consumption and CO₂ reduction as energy is progressively taken from SB

¹² The range equation of a conventional propulsion system is still represented by eq. 22 with $\varphi=0$ and by considering a parallel hybrid architecture.

Figure 23: ICE 2035 configuration - fuel consumption and CO2 reduction as energy is progressively taken from SB

Finally, a 90 pax turboprop based only on an ICE that will be equipped in 2050 with further technological enhancements ($e_{bat}=600$ Wh/kg, $e_{SB}=920^{13}$ Wh/kg, L/D=16, powertrain efficiency $\eta_1 \cdot \eta_3 = 0.40 \cdot 0.854$) will benefit significantly from the use of SB as displayed in Figure 24.

Figure 24: ICE 2050 configuration - fuel consumption and CO2 reduction as energy is progressively taken from SB

Table 28 summarizes the results relative to Figure 22 - Figure 24. The CO₂ reduction presented in the last column includes all of the technological improvements but it can easily be calculated that the CO₂ reduction due to the structural batteries alone is 638 kg with respect to the CO₂ emissions of 2023 without SB which corresponds to a percentage of approximately 10.

¹³ SB technology NG3 of Table 3

Table 28: ICE configuration - CO₂ reduction due to technological improvements

Config	Range [nm]	pax	Battery		Aero	Powertrain			Without SB		With SB		Because of SB utilization
			e_{bat} [Wh/kg]	e_{SB} [Wh/Δkg]		L/D [-]	η_1 [-]	η_3 [-]	E_{SB} [kWh]	Fuel [kg]	CO ₂ [kg]	Fuel [kg]	
ICE 2023	600	90	250	518	14	0.37	0.715	500	2037	6437	1935	6115	5%
ICE 2035	600	90	500	560	15	0.39	0.816	500	1728	5461	1682	5315	2.7%
ICE 2050	600	90	600	920	16	0.40	0.854	500	1536	4854	1482	4684	3.5%

When used for propulsive needs, structural batteries can be seen as part of the aircraft propulsion system¹⁴: two of the possible architectures are illustrated in Figure 25. To take into account the energy supplied by the structural batteries, eqq. 22 and 23 respectively for hybrid and full electric aircraft are updated as follow:

$$R = \eta_3 \frac{e_f}{g} \frac{L}{D} \left(\eta_1 + \eta_2 \frac{\varphi}{1 - \varphi} \right) \ln \frac{W_{OE} + W_{PL} + (g/e_{bat})E_{0,tot} \left(\varphi + (e_{bat}/e_f)(1 - \varphi) \right) - g \frac{E_{SB}}{e_{bat}} \left(1 - \frac{e_{bat}}{e_{SB}} \right)}{W_{OE} + W_{PL} + (g/e_{bat})\varphi E_{0,tot} - g \frac{E_{SB}}{e_{bat}} \left(1 - \frac{e_{bat}}{e_{SB}} \right)} \quad (25)$$

$$R = \eta_2 \eta_3 \frac{L}{D} \times \ln \frac{E_{0,tot}}{W_{OE} + W_{PL} + (g/e_{bat})E_{0,tot} + g \frac{E_{SB}}{e_{bat}} \left(1 - \frac{e_{bat}}{e_{SB}} \right)} \quad (26)$$

where E_{SB} and e_{SB} are the structural battery energy and specific energy based on delta weight, respectively.

Figure 25: Structural batteries into parallel (left) and series (right) hybrid propulsion architectures

The analysis is carried out only for the series architecture as it is particularly suitable for distributed propulsion concepts. It is worth noting that the conventional battery weight is limited by the maximum take-off weight (otherwise the airframe weight and fuselage drag increase accordingly) and the maximum landing weight in order not to reinforce the landing gear as the battery weight does not decrease as the energy is depleted.

¹⁴ It is assumed that Structural batteries have a discharge rate comparable to that of conventional batteries.

The exercise already done for non-propulsive needs has been repeated for propulsive needs and the results corresponding to the technological levels of 2023, 2025 and 2050 are displayed in Figure 26, Figure 27 and Figure 28 respectively.

Figure 26: Hybrid 2023 configuration - fuel consumption and CO₂ reduction as energy is progressively taken from SB

Figure 27: Hybrid 2035 configuration - fuel consumption and CO₂ reduction as energy is progressively taken from SB

Figure 28: Hybrid 2050 configuration - fuel consumption and CO₂ reduction as energy is progressively taken from SB

Table 29 highlights that the overall CO₂ reduction of hybrid aircraft is higher than that of conventional aircraft. This, of course, is an obvious result since there is less fuel on board due to the energy provided by the batteries. It can easily be calculated that the contribution of SB alone is 19% for hybrid aircraft, higher than that of conventional propulsion system and is due to the efficiency of the drivetrain components. Finally, the column of Table 29 containing the weight of the standard batteries simply says that their involvement is required as long as the specific energy is high.

Table 29: Hybrid configuration - CO₂ reduction due to technological improvements

Config	Range [nm]	pax	Conventional battery		Structural batteries		Aero	Powertrain		Without SB		With SB		Because of SB utilization
			e_{bat} [Wh/kg]	Weight [kg]	e_{SB} [Wh/kg]	E_{SB} [kWh]		L/D [-]	η_1 [-]	η_3 [-]	Fuel [kg]	CO ₂ [kg]	Fuel [kg]	
Hybrid 2023	600	90	250	360	518	1000	14	0.37	0.715	2160	6825	1944	6143	10%
Hybrid 2035	600	90	500	378	560	1000	15	0.39	0.816	1787	5647	1701	5375	4.8%
Hybrid 2050	600	90	600	1109	920	1000	16	0.40	0.854	1569	4958	1459	4610	7%

5. Conclusions

This deliverable has summarised the outcomes of the study on the scalability of the structural battery concept developed in SOLIFLY and the resulting technology roadmap based on the technological and TRL results obtained in the project.

Undoubtedly, the two SB concepts illustrated in the project represent a very challenging solution to achieve weight savings and, in view of the need expressed by the EU Green Deal and Clean Aviation programme for deep decarbonisation of air transport using advanced technologies.

The work shows that the current TRL of structural batteries for in-service applicability is still low for short-term results, but promising applications could be achieved for medium-term non-propulsive use in 2035 and for long-term propulsive use in 2050, in particular for the regional segment with consequent beneficial effects also in terms of decarbonisation.

The maturity of the applicability of the SB in the coming years is linked to many factors that must be taken into consideration and that in this document have been highlighted and, in some cases, considered already resolved in order to enable the elaborations and forecasts reported.

The contents of this document represent only a preliminary assessment that will have to be supplemented in subsequent projects with further assessments regarding mechanical properties, safety issues and certification.

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Project partners

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1. (Coord.)	AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH	Austria
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5.	UNINA	Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II	Italy
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